

Question Regarding Quantum Pure State Entropy and the Correspondence Principle

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In (1), it is stated that quantum entropy is given by $-\sum_p a(p)^* a(p) \ln\{a^*(p)a(p)\} - \int dx W^*(x)W(x) \ln\{W^*W\}$ ((1)), where $W(x)=\sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$. (1) states that the thermodynamic entropy is linked to energy and so is represented by: $-\sum_p a(p)^* a(p) \ln\{a^*(p)a(p)\}$ alone.

As a result, we consider the example of a quantum single particle in an infinite well potential of length L . If one uses ((1)) as the definition of entropy, then (2) states that the first term is proportional to $\ln(1/L)$ for $n \rightarrow \infty$ and the second, to $\ln(L)$ so the sum is independent of L . In other words, $dS=0$, if one changes the size of the box quantum adiabatically. In the $n \rightarrow \infty$ example, one should have essentially a classical result according to the correspondence principle, and so $dE = -FdL$. The first law of thermodynamics states that $dE = TdS(\text{thermo}) - FdL$ ($PdV = FdL$), so if $S(\text{thermo})$ is $-\sum_p a(p)^* a(p) \ln\{a^*(p)a(p)\}$, then this is proportional to $\ln(1/L)$ in the classical limit ($n \rightarrow \infty$) and one does not have $dE = FdL$ as one would expect classically.

First Law of Thermodynamics

The first law of thermodynamics in a simple form is:

$$dE = TdS(\text{thermo}) - PdV \quad ((1))$$

If $dS(\text{thermo})=0$, then $dE = -PdV$, with $P = \text{force/area} \rightarrow dE = -Fdx \quad ((2))$

((2)) holds for Newtonian mechanics. Thus, in Newtonian problems one simply does not include a dS term even if certain uncertainties (e.g. spatial) exist and even increase. For example, a particle moving in a box of length L has a position uncertainty proportional to $\ln(L)$. If the length is increased to $L+dL$, the length uncertainty increases to a value proportional to $\ln(L+dL)$, but this is informational entropy (uncertainty), not thermodynamic entropy (uncertainty). From a Newtonian point of view, this is a deterministic problem and information uncertainty is not an issue. Thus, $dS(\text{thermo}) = 0$ because $S(\text{thermo})$ is not a consideration in the first place.

Correspondence Principle

The correspondence principle suggests that when a quantum energy level approaches infinite, one should see classical (Newtonian) results. In particular, if $dS(\text{thermal})$ exists for n not infinite, then as $n \rightarrow \infty$, it should disappear for the particle in a box with an infinite potential, otherwise quantum mechanics and classical mechanics would be inconsistent in the $n \rightarrow \infty$ limit.

Information and Thermodynamic Entropy

In (1), it is stated that quantum entropy is:

$$- \sum p a^*(p)a(p) \ln\{a^*(p)a(p)\} - \int dx W^*(x)W(x) \ln(W^*W) \quad ((2))$$

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Here $W_n(x)$ =wavefunction = $\sum a(p) \exp(ipx)$ ((3)).

In (1), it is stated that only $-\sum p a^*(p)a(p) \ln\{a^*(p)a(p)\}$ represents thermodynamic entropy because such entropy is associated with energy and not uncertainty in space. The uncertainty in space $\exp(ipx)$ helps to fix the value of $a(p)$, but (1) suggests it is only the first term of ((2)) which is the thermodynamic entropy.

As a result, it seems that if the first term of ((2)) is a function of n and L for a particle in an infinite potential well, then for $n \rightarrow$ infinite, this result should not depend on L . If it did, the dS (thermodynamic) would be proportional to dL for a quantum adiabatic change in L and not 0 as in the Newtonian case.

Quantum Particle in an Infinite Well

According to (2), for a quantum particle in an infinite well of length L :

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \text{infinite}} -\sum p a^*(p)a(p) \ln\{a^*(p)a(p)\} = \ln(\text{constant}/L) \quad ((4))$$

$$- \int dx W^*(x)W(x) \ln(W^*W) = \ln(\text{constant}^2 L) \quad ((5))$$

As a result, in the $n \rightarrow$ infinite limit: $S = S_p + S_x = \text{constant}$, i.e. has no L dependence.

If one considers a state n (for $n \rightarrow$ infinite) with $E_n = n^2 \cdot 3.14^2 \cdot 3.14 / (LL)$ and quantum adiabatically changes the length of the well from L to $L+dL$, then:

$$dE_n = -2n^2 \cdot 3.14^2 \cdot 3.14 \cdot dL / (LLL) \quad ((6))$$

For $n \rightarrow$ infinite, this should be considered a Newtonian problem with dE_n described entirely by $-Fdx$. In other words, $dS(\text{thermal})$ should automatically be 0 as it is if $S(\text{thermal}) = S_p + S_x$, but not if $S(\text{thermal}) = S_p$, because then there is still a dependence on L in S_p .

Consideration of S_p

Even though S_x is due to uncertainty in position and S_p , by definition, is linked to uncertainty (or a spread) in p (momentum states), i.e. $a(p)$, the overall result for S_p depends on L . Classically, if one has a box of length L , then there is an uncertainty of L to find the particle at any x if p is constant. The quantum result gives S proportional to $\ln(L)$ which is also the classical result. The issue is that the length L affects the $a(p)$ spread because $p_{\text{ave}} = n \cdot 3.14 / L$. If the average p depends on L , the variance it seems should also, and does as explicitly shown in ((2)). Thus, it

is not surprising that S_p is also linked to $\ln(1/L)$. For an ideal gas in a box with no potential, the uncertainty in momentum piece is completely independent of L . This is not the case for S_p and so we suggest that even though p is linked to energy, one need not necessarily consider S_p the thermodynamic entropy as it is also influenced by space even for no potential within the box (only at the walls).

Conclusion

In conclusion, given that $S_{\text{quantum}} = \sum_p a^*(p)a(p) \ln\{a^*(p)a(p)\} - \int dx W^*(x)W(x) \ln(W^*W)$ we ask whether one may assign only the first term as representing S (thermodynamic). We consider a quantum particle in an infinite well and note that $S_x = \ln(c^2/L)$ and $S_p = \ln(c^2/L)$ for $n \rightarrow \text{infinite}$. Thus, for $n \rightarrow \text{infinite}$ $S_p + S_x = \text{constant}$ independent of L . Then $dS = 0$ for a quantum adiabatic change from L to $L+dL$. According to the correspondence principle, $n \rightarrow \text{infinite}$ means that Newtonian results must apply and equal quantum ones. In the Newtonian picture a change of dL with a change dE means: $dE = -\text{Force } dL$. In other words, $dS(\text{thermal}) = 0$, but if one uses S_p , it goes as $\ln(1/L)$ in this limit, suggests there is $dS(\text{thermodynamic})$ which does not vanish as $L \rightarrow L+dL$.

References

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